

Effect of age (20, 40, 60 days) and number of seedlings per hill on grain yield of rice varieties, 1977 wet season, Pantnagar, India.

Seedlings (no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)					
	Jaya			Pusa 2-21		
	20 d	40 d	60 d	20 d	40 d	60 d
2	6.8	6.5	4.9	7.3	6.0	4.6
4	7.5	5.7	5.7	7.3	6.2	5.2
6	7.4	6.6	5.0	7.4	6.7	5.4

Source of variation	Standard deviation of mean (±)	Coefficient of variation (%)	Coefficient of difference at 5%
Variety	0.3	19	
Seedling age	0.4		1.1
Seedlings/hill	0.4		1.1
Variety × age × seedlings/hill interaction	1.0		2.7

seedling number. The yield increased when the number of seedlings from the same age group rose from 2 to 6/hill (see table). The magnitude of yield reduction due to overaged seedlings was low for the medium-duration Jaya. The yield

increased with 2 and 4 seedlings of the same age group per hill, and 6 seedlings/hill for 40-day-old seedlings. The difference was probably due to a buildup in the insect population in a few plots. ■

Reduction of nursery area in wet cultivation of rice

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A study was conducted at Ambasamudram to determine the minimum area required for a seedbed and the optimum seeding rate.

Seedlings from the nursery seeded at 3, 6, and 9 kg/40 m² were healthier and stronger than those seeded at 12 kg/40 m². The seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² were taller than those seeded at the other rates. The number of leaves that each seedling produced did not differ among

the various treatments (see table).

When the seed rate was increased from 3 to 6 kg/40 m², the number of seedlings per unit area proportionally increased. When the seed rate was increased to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² the increase in the number of seedlings was not proportional. That might be attributable to the high mortality of seedlings at higher seed rates.

The seedlings from the nursery seeded at 6 kg/40 m², when spaced at 20 × 10 cm, covered twice the main field area covered by the seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m². Increasing the seeding rate to 9 and 12 kg/40 m² did not result in a proportional increase in the main field area covered.

Effect of nursery seeding rate on rice seedlings and wet cultivation of rice, Paddy Experiment Station, Tamil Nadu, India.

Seeding rate (kg/40 m ²)	Seedling ht (cm)	Leaves (no./seedling)	Seedlings (no./m ²)	Area (m ²) covered in the main field with seedlings	Seedbed required to transplant 1 ha main field (m ²)	Transplanting rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
3	30	4	3201	21	480	36	6.2
6	23	4	6024	40	252	38	5.6
9	22	4	6816	45	224	51	5.2
12	22	4	8027	53	188	57	4.9

C.D.: 0.4

However, the yield of seedlings seeded at 6 kg/40 m² was lower (5.6 t/ha) than that of seedlings seeded at 3 kg/40 m² (6.2 t/ha) (see table). Because yield was the ultimate deciding factor, the nursery seeded at 3 kg/40 m² was the most economically advantageous. ■

Response of transplanted rice to zinc application in Gangetic alluvial soils

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Improved rice varieties planted in alluvial soils often show symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly during early growth. Zinc deficiency is usually corrected by applying zinc to the soil or as a foliar spray. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production, an experiment was conducted with and without zinc. The zinc was applied at a rate of 16 kg/ha as soil application and 5 kg/ha as a foliar spray in kharif 1976 at the BHU Research Farm. The soil is medium-textured with a pH of 7.3.

Zinc as zinc sulfate was incorporated into the soil at final puddling; it was also sprayed at the tillering and booting growth stages. The effects of the two methods of zinc application on plant height, straw yield, and grain yield components were compared.

The experiment showed that alluvial soils are deficient in available zinc. Zinc application increased grain and straw yield significantly. Foliar-sprayed zinc increased yield by 17.2%; it also increased straw yield and 100-grain weight. Both soil and foliar application of zinc significantly affected plant height and number of grains per panicle. ■

Nitrogen management at moderate levels of nitrogen in lowland rice

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A field experiment on nitrogen